

Hybrid de novo genome assembly

Thursday 7 October 2021, 2-5pm AEDT/ 1-4pm AEST /
1:30-4:40pm ACDT/ 11am-2pm AWST

Lead Trainer: Grace Hall, Melbourne Bioinformatics

Facilitators:

Steven Morgan, Melbourne Bioinformatics
Dr Igor Makunin, QCIF Bioinformatics

Hosts: Dr Melissa Burke, Australian BioCommons

*Timings are approximate and subject to change

Time	Topic	Who
2:00 pm AEDT 1:00 pm AEST 1:30 pm ACDT 11:00 am AWST	Welcome and intro/housekeeping	Melissa
2:10 pm AEDT 1:10 pm AEST 1:40 pm ACDT 11:10am AWST	Introduction to de novo assembly Overview of workflow	Grace
2:30 pm AEDT 1:30 pm AEST 2:00 pm ACDT 11:30 am AWST	Connecting to Galaxy and importing data (hands-on) Accessing and running Flye (hands-on) Introduction to QC with Quast and Busco	Grace
2:45 pm AEDT 1:45 pm AEST 2:15 pm ACDT 11:45 am AWST	Breakout room 1 Assessing draft genome quality	All
2:55 pm AEDT 1:55 pm AEST 2:25 pm ACDT	Summary of QC results from Quast and Busco	Grace

11:55 am AWST		
3:05pm AEDT 2:05 pm AEST 2:35 pm ACDT 12:05 pm AWST	Introducing assembly polishing with Pilon	Grace
3:10 pm AEDT 2:10 pm AEST 2:40 pm ACDT 12:10 pm AWST	Breakout room 2 Execute Pilon on draft genome Execute Quast and Busco on polished genome	All
3:25 pm AEDT 2:25 pm AEST 2:55 pm ACDT 12:25 pm AWST	Reviewing QC results between draft and polished genomes	Grace
3:35 pm AEDT 2:35 pm AEST 3:05 pm ACDT 12:35 pm AWST	Introduction to Unicycler Execute Unicycler (hands-on)	Grace
3:40 pm AEDT 2:40 pm AEST 3:10 pm ACDT 12:40 pm AWST	Break	
3:55 pm AEDT 2:55 pm AEST 3:25 pm ACDT 12:55 pm AWST	Exploring Unicycler in more detail	Grace
4:05pm AEDT 3:05 pm AEST 3:35 pm ACDT 1:05 pm AWST	Breakout room 3 Execute Quast and Busco on Unicycler genome	All
4:20 pm AEDT 3:20 pm AEST 3:50 pm ACDT 1:20 pm AWST	Comparing results for different Unicycler parameters How to troubleshoot your assembly Tools for different assemblies Workflows for small & large genome assembly Summary and overview of what you have learnt	Grace
4:45 pm AEDT 3:45 pm AEST	Question time	Grace

4:15 pm ACDT 1:45 pm AWST		
4:55 pm AEDT 3:55 pm AEST 4:25 pm ACDT 1:55 pm AWST	Wrap up and feedback	Melissa
5:00pm AEDT 4:00 pm AEST 4:30 pm ACDT 2:00 pm AWST	Close	

Useful links

Training materials:

<https://www.melbournebioinformatics.org.au/tutorials/tutorials/assembly/assembly-protocol/>

Slides

https://www.melbournebioinformatics.org.au/tutorials/tutorials/hybrid_assembly/media/hybrid_assembly_slides.pdf

Galaxy Australia: usegalaxy.org.au